

Malacological news from the Czech and Slovak Republics in 2024

TOMÁŠ ČEJKA¹, LUBOŠ BERAN², MAREK ČILIAK³, RADOVAN COUFAL⁴, VERONIKA HORSÁKOVÁ⁴,
LUCIE JUŘIČKOVÁ⁵, ALENA KOCURKOVÁ⁵, MICHAL MAŇAS⁶, DAGMAR BERNEŠKA ŘÍHOVÁ⁷,
BRANISLAV TEJ⁸ & MICHAL HORSÁK⁴

¹Institute of Botany, Plant Science and Biodiversity Center, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Dúbravská cesta 9, SK-845 23 Bratislava, Slovakia, e-mail: t.cejka@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6485-5660>

²Regional Office Kokořínsko – Máchův kraj Protected Landscape Area Administration, Nature Conservation Agency of the Czech Republic, Česká 149, CZ-276 01 Mělník, Czechia, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5851-6048>

³Department of Applied Ecology, Faculty of Ecology and Environmental Sciences, Technical University in Zvolen, T. G. Masaryka 24, SK-960 01, Zvolen, Slovakia, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6720-9365>

⁴Department of Botany and Zoology, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Kotlářská 2, CZ-611 37 Brno, Czechia,

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5870-5041>

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3264-7728>

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2742-2740>

⁵Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Viničná 7, CZ-128 44 Praha 2, Czechia,

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5163-1222>

 <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-1552-3815>

⁶Táboritů 23, CZ-779 00 Olomouc, Czechia, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2697-5140>

⁷Department of Biology and Environmental Studies, Faculty of Education, Charles University, Magdalény Rettigové 4, CZ-116 39 Praha, Czechia, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2122-130X>

⁸Department of Ecology, Faculty of Humanities and Natural Sciences, University of Prešov, ul. 17. novembra 1, SK-080 01 Prešov, Slovakia, <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-8344-6768>

ČEJKA T., BERAN L., ČILIAK M., COUFAL R., HORSÁKOVÁ V., JUŘIČKOVÁ L., KOCURKOVÁ A., MAŇAS M., ŘÍHOVÁ D. B., TEJ B. & HORSÁK M., 2025: Malacological news from the Czech and Slovak Republics in 2024. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 24: 24–36. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2025-24-24>

Publication date: 25. 7. 2025.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Public License.

This article presents important faunistic records carried out in the Czech and Slovak Republics in 2024. In 2024, many new records were made for non-native and currently spreading species such as for example *Cornu aspersum*, *Krynickyllus melanocephalus*, *Sinanodonta woodiana*, and *Tandonia kusceri*. *Krynickyllus melanocephalus* was recorded in Czechia for the first time. *Melanoides tuberculata* was confirmed at two outdoor sites in Slovakia, where it forms stable populations. The records of several native species include findings of protected and rare species (e.g. *Euglesa pseudosphaerium*, *Gyraulus rossmaessleri*, and *Planorbis carinatus*), but also still poorly known species (*Euglesa globularis*, and *Sphaerium nucleus*). In a separate section, we present records of two unintentionally introduced species reported for the first time for these countries from greenhouses (*Ambigolimax parvipenis* and *Oxychilus translucidus*).

Key words: mollusc fauna, faunistic survey, new records, species list

Introduction

The last comprehensive monograph on molluscs of the Czech and Slovak Republics was published in 2013 (HORSÁK et al. 2013). Since 2020 we are publishing annually malacological news from the territory of the former Czechoslovakia to keep track of new important records. The previous summary of new records covers the years 2015–2019 (ČEJKA et al. 2020), 2020 (ČEJKA et al. 2021), 2021 (ČEJKA et al. 2022), 2022 (BERAN et al. 2023), 2023 (ČEJKA et al. 2024). All these new data are used to regularly update an annotated checklist of molluscs and distribution maps of selected species (HORSÁK et al. 2025). In this follow-up paper, we present important faunistic records carried out in the Czech and Slovak Republics in 2024.

The rules for selecting records are (i) the first record in Bohemia, Moravia, or Slovakia, (ii) a regionally significant new record, (iii) new and important records of species listed in NATURA 2000 and the national Red Lists as critically endangered or endangered species (usually excluding records of regularly monitored sites and populations), or (iv) recently introduced and currently spreading non-native species.

Since 2024, data on unintentionally introduced species have been listed in a separate section. These species are usually found in greenhouses, garden centres, and shops selling ornamental stoneware. They are introduced through natural and other materials or as “stowaways” with cargo or animal vectors. They also include thermophilic species that can only survive in thermal and artificially heated wa-

ter bodies. Detailed information on the occurrence of the individual species follows in the text, and the records are given (Tab. 1).

Species recorded outdoors

Ambigolimax valentianus (A. Férussac, 1821)

It is a synanthropic slug species originally native to the Iberian Peninsula. It has spread widely across Europe and other continents through horticultural trade and human activities. A single adult specimen, whose identification was confirmed by genital features, was found in a vegetable garden in Olomouc (Fig. 1). Survival outdoors has not yet been confirmed but is possible in the future due to climate warming. There are possible source populations, as the species was already found in 2012 in the palm greenhouse Flora Olomouc and in 2012–2013 in the Palacký University greenhouses in Šlechtitelů Street (M. Mañas, unpublished data). We do not consider the species to be part of the Czech outdoor malacofauna, as with the other accidental records of *Testacella haliotidea* in Prague (PODROUŽKOVÁ 2022) and *Helicigona lapicida* in Slovakia (REPASKÝ et al. 2025).

Charpentieria ornata (Rossmässler, 1836)

A clausiliid species with a main distribution area in south-east Austria, Slovenia, and north-west Croatia (WELTER-SCHULTES 2012). In Czechia, isolated occurrences are known from the Orlické hory Mts in eastern Bohemia and some isolated sites from northern and central Moravia

Fig. 1. *Ambigolimax valentianus* from Olomouc, Czechia. Photo by M. Mañas.

(HORSÁK et al. 2013). A rich population of dozens of individuals was discovered on one of the inactive upper floors in the Vitošov limestone quarry (Fig. 2). This new site is about 23 km away from the nearest known population in the Špraněk National Natural Monument near Javoříčko. It is the most abundant species among the other four species found in the surveyed plot.

Fig. 2. An inactive upper floor of the Vitošov quarry where newly discovered population of *Charpentieria ornata* lives. Photo taken on 18th of May, 2024 by R. Coufal.

Corbicula fluminea (O. F. Müller, 1774)

Seven new records have been confirmed from the eastern part of Slovakia. Five sites come from the Zemplínska Šírava reservoir, where the species was found at all sites during a survey of the shore areas. The largest number of living individuals was found at the site near the village of Lúčky. The other two sites were located in the littoral of large lowland rivers, in the river Ondava near the village of Hraň (below the confluence of the Ondava and Trnávka rivers) and the Tisa on the sandy bank of Trakanská riviéra near the village of Malé Trakany. All finds originate from sandy or fine-grained substrates. The record from the river Sázava in Týnec nad Sázavou in Central Bohemia, Czechia, confirmed upstream spread in this river.

Cornu aspersum (O. F. Müller, 1774)

There are seven new records from Slovakia, one new record is from Czechia. Including previous records (ČEJKA et al. 2020, 2021, 2022, 2024, BERAN et al. 2023), 22 sites in Czechia and 17 sites in Slovakia are known in total.

Dreissena rostriformis (Deshayes, 1838)

The second record of this non-native species in Slovakia comes from the lower reaches of the Váh River. The first record was published by ČEJKA et al. (2020) as *Dreissena bugensis*.

Euglesa globularis (Clessin, 1873)

Since 2015, 18 new sites have been reported in Czechia (ČEJKA et al. 2020, 2021, 2022, BERAN et al. 2023, ČEJKA et al. 2024) and two sites in Slovakia (ČEJKA et al. 2022, 2024). A new record is reported from a wetland in southern Bohemia.

Euglesa pseudosphaerium (J. Favre, 1927)

In 2024, the occurrence of numerous populations of this critically endangered species was confirmed in the Řežabinec National Natural Monument in South Bohemia (BERAN 2025), where it was found for the first time in 2014 (BERAN 2016). Since 2015, 20 new sites have been recorded in Czechia (ČEJKA et al. 2020, 2022, BERAN et al. 2023, ČEJKA et al. 2024). It is also a very rare species in Slovakia, occurring mainly in the Danube basin, in East Slovakia, one site is known from the lake of Malá Izra in Slanské vrchy Mts (BRABENEC coll., depon. in Slovak National Museum – Natural History Museum).

Ferrissia californica (Rowell, 1873)

Three new records of this non-native gastropod are reported from the western edge of Bohemia, outside its known range (ČEJKA et al. 2020).

Gyraulus parvus (Say, 1817)

The new records of this species come from the Krušné hory Mts in north-west Bohemia outside its known distribution area. In Slovakia, unlike in Czechia, the occurrence of this species was not monitored; a breakthrough was only achieved in 2016, when L. Beran began mapping in Slovakia. So far, 20 sites are known from Slovakia (ČEJKA et al. 2020, 2021, BERAN et al. 2023).

Gyraulus rossmaessleri (Schmidt, 1852)

This rare snail inhabits temporary pools and wetlands and is scattered in Czechia and the south-western part of Slovakia (ČEJKA et al. 2020). Since 2015, 11 new sites have been reported in Czechia (ČEJKA et al. 2020, 2022, 2024). The occurrence of this endangered gastropod was confirmed at several sites in northwestern Bohemia near Teplice.

Helix lucorum Linnaeus, 1758

Two new records come from the Slovakian town of Nitra, where this species has become established and is widespread in this town, especially along the Nitra River (ČEJKA et al. 2020).

Hygromia cinctella (Draparnaud, 1801)

Two new localities of this species have been recorded in western Slovakia. The first record of this species in Brno, Czechia, was made in the city centre. It occurs sympatrically with two other non-native species, *Cornu aspersum* and *Tandonia kusceri* (ČEJKA et al. 2020).

Krynickillus melanocephalus Kaleniczenko, 1851

In 2024, three new localities of this slug species were identified near its first occurrence in Slovakia from 2020 (ČEJKA et al. 2021) and in the cemetery of Lučatín in central Slovakia, about 150 km from the previously reported sites. In October 2024, the species was sighted for the first time in Czechia, in the Dolní Šárka district of Prague, where it was found exclusively in rotting fallen wood, layers of bark or tree litter (ŘÍHOVÁ et al. 2025). At the same time, the species was also found in Hradec Králové (Fig. 3).

Melanoides tuberculata (O. F. Müller, 1774)

This freshwater gastropod is native to northern Africa and southern Asia (NECK 1985). It has become invasive in many tropical and subtropical regions worldwide, primarily through the aquarium trade and accidental introductions (KARATAYEV et al. 2009). The species was recorded for the first time in Czechia in an open environment. A very abundant population was found in the stream Skryjský potok, which drains from the cooling water reservoir of the Dukovany nuclear power plant (COUFAL & BERAN 2024). It was previously reported from four sites in Slovakia (Fig. 4), all of them are fed by thermal water. Two sites are in the Váh catchment: small ponds in the Piešťany spa park (LIPTÁK et al. 2018) and the stream Čepčinský potok in Turčianske Teplice (MÁJSKY 2000). Two sites are in the Nitra catchment: the stream Teplý potok in Opatovce nad Nitrou (LIPTÁK et al. 2016, 2018) and the canal Chalmová in Bystričany – Chalmová (MÁJSKY 2000). Two sites (canal Chalmová and the stream Čepčinský potok) were resampled in 2024, hosting viable populations.

Odhnneripisidium moitessierianum (Paladilhe, 1866)

This rare and endangered pea mussel living mostly in the muddy sediments of streams was in 2024 found in the canal Malá Ohře. Since 2015, only six new sites of this species have been recorded in Czechia (ČEJKA et al. 2020, 2022).

Pisidium amnicum (O. F. Müller, 1774)

In Czechia, this rare and endangered species occurs in streams. Since 2015, up to 57 new sites have been recorded in Czechia, while only one site has been recorded in Slovakia (ČEJKA et al. 2020, 2022; BERAN 2023). According to historical data from before 2015 (VAVROVÁ 2009), this species is not so rare in natural watercourses in Slovakia; the low number of recent records is related to the lack of systematic surveys of natural watercourses in the last decade. In 2024, the occurrence of this pea mussel was confirmed in the river Ohře and the canal Malá Ohře. A small population was discovered in the small stream of Bolíkovský potok, that is a tributary of the river Moravská Dyje in south Bohemia.

Planorbis carinatus O. F. Müller, 1774

The finding of this endangered gastropod in the river Moravská Dyje is out of its known range in Czechia. The occurrence was also confirmed in the river Ohře in Košnice in northwestern Bohemia. Since 2015, 21 new sites are known in Czechia (ČEJKA et al. 2020, 2022).

Potamopyrgus antipodarum (J. E. Gray, 1843)

In 2024, four new sites outside its known range (HORSÁK et al. 2025) were discovered. This non-native species was found in the river Jizera in northern Bohemia and the river Moravská Dyje situated in southern Bohemia.

Fig. 3. Map of the current distribution of *Krynickillus melanocephalus* in Czechia and Slovakia. M<R = increasing occurrences.

Fig. 4. Known outdoor records of *Melanoides tuberculata* in Czechia and Slovakia. M<R = increasing occurrences.

Pupilla triplicata (Studer, 1820)

This steppe calcicole species is recently in decline in many sites across the Bohemian Karst. Based on previous field experience, it is very difficult to find live individuals. Therefore, the discovery of living individuals from 2024 in the Kobyla quarry in the Bohemian Karst is unique. This locality has been studied by malacologists for a long time and the species *P. triplicata* has not yet been recorded there.

Sinanodonta woodiana (Lea, 1834)

This species first appeared and began to spread in Slovakia in 1994, where it was collected by ŠTEFFEK et al. (2005) in a floodplain of the river Ipel' near Tešmak and by KOŠEL (1995) in a floodplain of the Danube in Čičov (ŠTEFFEK 2007). The occurrence of this species since its first record in the Danube (KOŠEL 1995) has not yet been reported from eastern Slovakia. In 2024, we found this species at seven locations in the Tisa catchment. At one site (Stretávka) it was extremely abundant with an average of 44 individuals per m². The size of the largest mussel was 22.9 cm and the weight of 61 living individuals was 23.45 kg. In Czechia this species is also known from the river Odra (e. g. ČEJKA et al. 2021) and in 2024 the new record which confirmed its occurrence comes from the oxbow of this river near the Czech-Polish border. A new record also comes from the Vysočina Region.

Sphaerium nucleus (Studer, 1820)

In the past, this rare species was not distinguished from the euryoecious *Euglesa casertana* on the territory of the former Czechoslovakia (HORSÁK & NEUMANOVÁ 2004). Since 2015, 74 new sites have been recorded in Czechia, but only one in Slovakia (ČEJKA et al. 2020, 2022). We assume that Slovakia has a similar island-like distribu-

tion in natural waters as Czechia. The reason for the low number of records is that research on aquatic habitats has mainly focused on urban areas in the last decade. In 2024, the species was found at several new sites, mostly in the Vysočina Region and also in the Jizera river basin in central Bohemia and the wetlands in the Řežabinec National Nature Reserve in southern Bohemia (BERAN 2025).

Tandonia kusceri (H. Wagner, 1931)

This non-native snail first appeared in Slovakia in 2014 (KORÁBEK et al. 2016) and is spreading quite rapidly in urban and suburban areas. Most of the previous records come from the south-west of Slovakia, but as part of the ongoing nationwide survey of urban habitats, we have also recorded numerous populations in more eastern parts of Slovakia. In 2024, we recorded another 11 sites in Slovakia (Fig. 5). One site was also discovered in Czechia, where this species was recorded for the first time in 2021 (ČEJKA et al. 2024).

Unio crassus Philipsson, 1788, ***Unio nanus*** Lamarck, 1819

In 2024, the occurrence of populations of these species was confirmed in several rivers in Czechia and new sites were also found. In the Vysočina Region, the occurrence was confirmed in the small stream Hejlovka. The population there appears to be very large in perspective (estimated at thousands of individuals). The results of the current survey are significantly better than the results of the 2017 survey (BERAN 2020). The new population was found in the stream Sázavka in the same region. In north-west Bohemia, an abundant population was discovered in the small stream Liboc, that is a tributary of the river Ohře. In South Bohemia, an extensive population was found in the river Moravská Dyje on the Czech-Austrian border. The

Fig. 5. An albino individual of *Tandonia kusceri* from the cemetery in Detva, Slovakia. Photo by M. Čiliak.

occurrence is particularly numerous in the border section, and it can therefore be assumed that a large population also occurs in the Austrian part of the river. In contrast, the occurrence in the Czech part upstream of this river is gradually declining. In Slovakia, the presence of numerous populations in the river Orava has been confirmed (BERAN et al. 2024). As the current identification of these species is not possible without the use of molecular genetic methods, tissue samples were taken for later analysis.

Vertigo geyeri Lindholm, 1925

It is a specialist of relict alkaline fens, sensitive to a stable water regime (SCHENKOVÁ et al. 2012). Currently, about 30 sites are known from Czechia (HORSÁKOVÁ & HORSÁK 2018, ČEJKA et al. 2020, HORSÁK et al. 2025). A single living individual was found by eye (sic!) in the Žemlička Nature Monument, a small alkaline fen in southern Bohemia. It is a reminder that some populations can be very low-abundant and difficult to detect, as the site was previously quantitatively sampled (M. HORSÁK, unpublished data), yet the species was not detected. It is the third known population in southern Bohemia, close to the much larger site, Brouskův mlýn National Nature Reserve, which also hosts *V. lilljeborgi*.

Viviparus acerosus (Bourguignat, 1862)

The other new site outside its native range was found in a pond in the Vysočina Region. In this region, this species is becoming relatively common in some ponds, probably due to the existence of an extensive population in the Švihov reservoir (BERAN et al. 2019, ČEJKA et al. 2020, 2024).

Non-native species in greenhouses and other man-made or man-influenced habitats

Ambigolimax parvipenis Hutchinson, Reise & Schlitt, 2022

It is the first record from Slovakia, morphologically and genetically confirmed (Fig. 6). The individual was found in the tropical section of the greenhouse at the Bratislava Botanical Garden. The original distribution of this slug is unknown (HUTCHINSON et al. 2022). From Europe, records are known from Great Britain (HUTCHINSON et al. 2022), Spain (including the Canary and Chafarinas Islands), France, Hungary (TURÓCI et al. 2023) and Greece (HUTCHINSON et al. 2022). In North America, it is widespread in California (HART et al. 2023), with one record from Arizona (HUTCHINSON et al. 2022).

Oxychilus translucidus (Mortillet, 1853)

A rich colony was found in the greenhouse of the Botanical Garden in the Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno (Fig. 7A, 7B, 7D). It is the first record of this species in Czechia. The species has been recorded in European greenhouses for more than 100 years, but records are rare (RIEDEL 1964, KOVTUN et al. 2017). It was introduced into Europe in the 1920s, now having rare records across Eastern and Central Europe, with the first record in Poland found in a greenhouse in the Warsaw botanical garden in 1929 (RIEDEL 1964).

The origin is not certain, assumed to be West Caucasian endemic (STWORZEWICZ 2008–2014). It can be easily identified by yellowish mucus (Fig. 7C).

Acknowledgements

We thank the following people for providing data on the occurrence of species and for their help in identifying species: Jaroslav Beran, Karel Beran, Monika Budzáková, Juraj Čáčaný, Ján Čapka, Jakub Fedorčák, Michal Hájek, John M. C. Hutchinson, Kristína Juričková, Dominik Roman Letz, Rudolf Masarovič, Andrej Mock, Marta Nandrážiová, Tomáš Navara, Pavol Purgat, Erika Šlachťová, and Petra Vörösová.

This work was supported by the Scientific Grant Agency of the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic and the Slovak Academy of Sciences (VEGA, project No. 2/0044/22). This work was supported by project COOPERATIO (COOP).

References

- BERAN L., 2016: *Pisidium pseudosphaerium* Favre, 1927 (Bivalvia: Sphaeriidae) in the Czech Republic – rare or overlooked? – *Folia Malacologica*, 24(2): 57–62. <https://doi.org/10.12657/folmal.024.005>
- BERAN L., 2020: Vodní měkkýši Sázavy a vybraných přítoků se zaměřením na ohrožené a nepůvodní druhy [Aquatic molluscs of the Sázava River and its selected tributaries with a focus on threatened and non-native species]. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 19: 29–54. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2020-19-29> (in Czech)
- BERAN L., 2025: Společenstva vodních měkkýšů NPP Řežabinec se zaměřením na vzácné a ohrožené druhy [Aquatic mollusc communities of the Řežabinec National Natural Monument with a focus on rare and endangered species]. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 24: 8–16. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2025-24-8> (in Czech)
- BERAN L., ČEJKA T., ADAMCOVÁ T., COUFAL R., ČAČANÝ J., HORÁČKOVÁ J., JUŘIČKOVÁ L., PODROUŽKOVÁ Š., ŘÍHOVÁ D., ŠLACHTOVÁ E. & HORSÁK M., 2023: Malacological news from the Czech and Slovak Republics in 2022. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 22: 37–47. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2023-22-37>
- BERAN L., HORSÁK M. & HOFMAN S., 2019: First records of *Viviparus acerosus* Bourguignat, 1862 (Gastropoda: Vivipariidae) from the Czech Republic outside its native range. – *Folia Malacologica*, 27(3): 223–229. <https://doi.org/10.12657/folmal.027.021>
- BERAN L., ŠLACHTOVÁ E., KLOBUŠICKÁ V. & BERAN J., 2024: Společenstva vodních měkkýšů řeky Oravy [Aquatic mollusc communities of the river Orava]. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 23: 111–116. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2024-23-111> (in Czech)
- COUFAL R. & BERAN L., 2024: First occurrence of *Melanoides tuberculata* (O. F. Müller, 1774) in an open environment in the Czech Republic. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 23: 34–36. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2024-23-34>
- ČEJKA T., BERAN L., ADAMCOVÁ T., BRONIŠOVÁ V., COUFAL R., ČILIAK M., DRVOTOVÁ M., HORÁČKOVÁ J., HORSÁKOVÁ V., JUŘIČKOVÁ L., KOCURKOVÁ A., KORÁBEK O., PODROUŽKOVÁ Š., ŘÍHOVÁ D. B., ŠLACHTOVÁ E. & HORSÁK M., 2024: Malacological news from the Czech and Slovak Republics in 2023 – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 23: 69–83. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2024-23-69>
- ČEJKA T., BERAN L., COUFAL R., DVOŘÁK L., HLAVÁČ J. Č.,

Fig. 6. Neighbour-joining tree constructed using COI gene sequence. Bootstrap values higher than 85, based on 10,000 runs, are indicated along the branches. Sequences were retrieved from GenBank and are shown with their accession number and original species names. Sequences of *Lehmannia carpatica* and *L. marginata* were used as outgroup. The newly generated sequence is marked in yellow. The protocols of DNA extraction, PCR amplification and sequencing followed those described in Horsáková et al. (2022).

Fig. 7. *Oxychilus translucidus* found in a tropical greenhouse in the Botanical Garden of the Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno, Czechia: A-B, live adults; C, sole mucus of *O. translucidus* (photographed on a white paper; width of the image = 5 mm); D, habitat of the recorded individuals hiding under these flower pots. Photos by M. Horsák.

- HORÁČKOVÁ J., HORSÁKOVÁ V., JUŘIČKOVÁ L., KOSOVÁ T., ČAČANÝ J., SZÁBOVÁ D., ŘÍHOVÁ D., TEJ B. & HORSÁK M., 2021: Malacological news from the Czech and Slovak Republics in 2020. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 20: 56–74. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2021-20-56>
- ČEJKA T., BERAN L., KORÁBEK O., HLAVÁČ J. Č., HORÁČKOVÁ J., COUFAL R., DRVOTOVÁ M., MAŇAS M., HORSÁKOVÁ V. & HORSÁK M., 2020: Malacological news from the Czech and Slovak Republics in 2015–2019. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 19: 71–106. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2020-19-71>
- ČEJKA T., BERAN L., COUFAL R., DVOŘÁK L., HORÁČKOVÁ J., HORSÁKOVÁ V., JUŘIČKOVÁ L., KORÁBEK O., ADAMCOVÁ T., SZÁBOVÁ D., ŠKODOVÁ J. & HORSÁK M., 2022: Malacological news from the Czech and Slovak Republics in 2021. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 21: 49–62. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2022-21-49>
- HART C. J., SANDBERG D. C., ASCHE M., DE LA RIVA D. G., BARTMAN G. G., BURKE A. F., BRABANT P. J. & ROBINSON D. G., 2023: Confirmation of established populations of *Ambigolimax parvipenis* Hutchinson, Reise and Schlitt, 2022 (Gastropoda: Limacidae) in San Diego County, California, USA. – *American Malacological Bulletin*, 40(1): 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.4003/006.040.0108>
- HORSÁK M., JUŘIČKOVÁ L. & PICKA J., 2013: Měkkýši České a Slovenské republiky. Molluscs of the Czech and Slovak Republics. – Kabourek, Zlín, 264 pp. (in Czech and English).
- HORSÁK M., ČEJKA T., JUŘIČKOVÁ L., BERAN L., HORÁČKOVÁ J., DVOŘÁK L., COUFAL R., MAŇAS M. & HORSÁKOVÁ V., 2025: Check-list and distribution maps of the molluscs of the Czech and Slovak Republics – online at <http://mollusca.sav.sk/malacology/checklist.htm>, checklist updated at June 13, 2025, maps updated at July 17, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15662117>
- HORSÁK M. & NEUMANOVÁ K., 2004: Distribution of *Pisidium globulare* Clessin, 1873 (Mollusca: Bivalvia) in the Czech Republic and Slovakia with notes to its ecology and morphological characters. – *Journal of Conchology*, 38(4): 373–381. <https://doi.org/10.5962/p.408153>
- HORSÁKOVÁ V. & HORSÁK M., 2018: Vrkoč Geyerův a vrkoč útlý – první nálezy celoevropsky ohrožených plžů ve Slavkovském lese [*Vertigo geyeri* and *Vertigo angustior* – first findings of pan-European endangered snails in Slavkovský les]. – *Arnika*, 2018(1): 30–33. (in Czech)
- HORSÁKOVÁ V., LÍZNAROVÁ E., RAZKIN O., NEKOLA J. C. & HORSÁK M., 2022: Deciphering “cryptic” nature of European rock-dwelling *Pyramidula* snails (Gastropoda: Stylommatophora). – *Contributions to Zoology*, 91(4–5): 233–260. <https://doi.org/10.1163/18759866-bja10032>
- HUTCHINSON J. M. C., REISE H. & SCHLITT B., 2022: Will the real *Limax nyctelius* please step forward: *Lehmannia*, *Ambigolimax*, or *Malacolimax*? No, *Letourneuxia*! – *Archiv für Molluskenkunde*. 151: 19–41. <https://doi.org/10.1127/arch.moll/151/019-041>
- KARATAYEV A. Y., BURLAKOVA L. E., KARATAYEV V. A. & PADILLA D. K., 2009: Introduction, distribution, spread, and impacts of exotic freshwater gastropods in Texas. – *Hydrobiologia*, 619: 181–194. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-008-9639-y>
- KAUPOVÁ A., 2024: *Krynickyllus melanocephalus*. – iNaturalist, online at <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/246935445>, published October 12, 2024.
- KORÁBEK O., ČEJKA T. & DVOŘÁK L., 2016: *Tandonia kusceri* (Pulmonata: Milacidae), a slug new for Slovakia. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 15: 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2016-15-3>
- KOŠEL V., 1995: The first record of *Anodonta woodiana* (Mollusca, Bivalvia) in Slovakia. – *Acta Zoologica Universitatis Comenianae*, 39: 3–7.
- KOVTUN O. A., VARGOVITSH R. S., SON M. O. & BALASHOV I. A., 2017: Invasive land snail *Oxychilus translucidus* (Stylommatophora, Zonitidae) in the catacombs of Odesa (Ukraine). – *Vestnik zoologii*, 51(4): 353–354. <https://doi.org/10.1515/vzoo-2017-0041>
- LETZ D. R., 2024: *Hygromia cinctella*. – iNaturalist, online at <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/240889759>, published September 10, 2024.
- LIPTÁK B., LIPTÁKOVÁ P., VESELÝ L. & KOUBA A., 2018: Length frequency and morphometric analysis of the non-indigenous red-rimmed melania (*Melanoides tuberculata*) populations in Slovakia. – *Biologia*, 73: 505–511. <https://doi.org/10.2478/s11756-018-0060-3>
- LIPTÁK B., MRUGALA A., PEKÁRIK L., MUTKOVIČ A., GRUEA D., PETRUSEK A. & KOUBA A., 2016: Expansion of the marbled crayfish in Slovakia: beginning of an invasion in the Danube catchment? – *Journal of Limnology*, 75: 305–312. <https://doi.org/10.4081/jlimnol.2016.1313>
- MÁJSKY J., 2000: Ichtyofauna termálnych vôd Podunajskej nížiny a Hornonitrianskej kotliny [Ichthyofauna of thermal waters in the lowland Podunajská nížina and in the basin Hornonitrianská kotlina]. – *Ochrana prírody*, 18: 155–160. (in Slovak)
- NECK R. W., 1985: *Melanoides tuberculata* in extreme Southern Texas. – *Texas Conchologist*, 21(4): 150–152.
- PODROUŽKOVÁ Š., 2022: The first record of carnivorous semislug *Testacella haliotidea* Draparnaud, 1801 in Czechia. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 21: 63–64. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2022-21-63>
- REPASKÝ J., ŘÍHOVÁ D., KUBÍKOVÁ K., COUFAL R., ORAVEC J. & JUŘIČKOVÁ L., 2025: Ulitníky pseudokrasovej tiesňavy Parkaň v pohorí Bachureň na východnom Slovensku [Gastropods of the Parkaň pseudokarst gorge in the Bachureň Mountains in Eastern Slovakia]. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 24: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2025-24-1> (in Slovak)
- RIEDEL A., 1964: Kaukaski šlimak *Oxychilus (Ortizius) komarowi* (O. Bttg.) w Polsce i w Bułgarii (*Gastropoda, Zonitidae*) [Caucasian snail *Oxychilus (Ortizius) komarowi* (O. Bttg.) in Poland and in Bulgaria (Gastropoda, Zonitidae)]. – *Fragmenta Faunistica*, 11(6): 75–82. <https://www.doi.org/10.3161/00159301FF1964.11.6.075> (in Polish)
- ŘÍHOVÁ D., KOCURKOVÁ A. & JUŘIČKOVÁ L., 2025: Jednonohý cestovateľ slimáčkovce černoahlavý (*Krynickyllus melanocephalus*) poprvé v Česku [The single-legged traveller, slug *Krynickyllus melanocephalus*, for the first time in Czechia]. – In: *Zoologické dny Brno 2025*. BRYJA J., HORSÁK M. & HORSÁKOVÁ V. (eds), *Sborník abstraktů z konference 13.–14. února 2025*: 189–190. (in Czech)
- SCHENKOVÁ V., HORSÁK M., PLESKOVÁ Z. & PAWLIKOWSKI P., 2012: Habitat preferences and conservation of *Vertigo geyeri* (Gastropoda: Pulmonata) in Slovakia and Poland. – *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 78(1): 105–111. <https://doi.org/10.1093/mollusc/eyr046>
- ŠTEFFEK J., 2007: Current knowledge of the distribution of invasive mollusc species in Slovakia. – *Folia Malacologica*, 15(1): 45–48. <https://doi.org/10.12657/folmal.015.004>
- ŠTEFFEK J., FALNIOWSKI A. & SZAROWSKA M., 2005: Príspevok k topografickému výskumu malakofauny okresu Levice [Contribution to the topographic malacological survey in the Levice District, SW Slovakia]. – *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca*, 4: 21–25. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2005-4-21>
- STWORZEWICZ E., 2008–2014: *Oxychilus translucidus* (Mortillet, 1854). – *Gatunki obce w faunie Polski* [Alien species in Polish fauna], Instytut Ochrony Przyrody PAN. – Online at <https://www.iop.krakow.pl/gatunkiobce/default0fe9.html>, cited June 11, 2025. (in Polish)
- TURÓCI Á., HUTCHINSON J. M. C., SCHLITT B., REISE H., RAPALA M. & PÁLL-GERGELY B., 2023: Five new introduced terrestrial

slugs in Hungary. – *BioInvasions Records*, 12: 711–729. <https://doi.org/10.3391/bir.2023.12.3.08>

VAVROVÁ L., 2009: Ekosozologická typizácia malakofauny Slovenska s využitím GIS [Ecosozological typification of the malacofauna of Slovakia using GIS]. – PhD. thesis, Ústav

ekológie lesa SAV, Zvolen, 90 pp. + maps. (in Slovak)

WELTER-SCHULTES F., 2012: European non-marine molluscs, a guide for species identification. – Planet Poster Editions, Göttingen, 679 pp. ISBN 3-933922-75-5, 978-3-3-933922-75-5

Table 1. Location data of the newly discovered occurrences reported herein. Greenhouse records are on gray background.

Species; live/empty; Nearest municipality; Coordinates (°N, °E); Location (briefly) and habitat; Date of coll.; Altitude; leg./det.
<i>Ambigolimax parvipenis</i> Hutchinson, Reise & Schlitt, 2022; 1/0; Bratislava; 48.1469, 17.0726; botanical garden greenhouse; 30. 3. 2024; 130; J. Čapka leg., M. Horsák, J. M. C. Hutchinson det. (GenBank accession number PV929586)
<i>Ambigolimax valentianus</i> (A. Férussac, 1821); 1/0; Olomouc; 49.5993, 17.2817; Táboritů 23, outdoor vegetable garden, compost; 21. 7. 2024; 214; M. Mañas leg., M. Mañas, M. Horsák det. (Fig. 1)
<i>Charpentieria ornata</i> (Rossmässler, 1836); 50/50; Hrabová, Vitošov; 49.8680, 16.9453; limestone quarry, on the margin of the inactive floor; 18. 5. 2024; 330; R. Coufal
<i>Corbicula fluminea</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 0/20; Týnec nad Sázavou; 49.8325, 14.5964; the river Sázava downstream of the weir; 22. 6. 2024; 240; L. Beran
<i>Corbicula fluminea</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 0/70; Klokočov; 48.8089, 22.0413; litoral of the water reservoir; 2. 12. 2024; 109; J. Fedorčák leg., B. Tej det.
<i>Corbicula fluminea</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 15/50; Vinné; 48.7962, 21.9779; litoral of the water reservoir; 12. 12. 2024; 115; B. Tej
<i>Corbicula fluminea</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 14/2; Hraň; 48.5355, 21.8058; river Ondava, S of the village; 9. 9. 2024; 100; B. Tej
<i>Corbicula fluminea</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 4/7; Malé Trakany; 48.3942, 22.1446; Trakanská riviéra, river Tisa; 9. 9. 2024; 103; B. Tej
<i>Corbicula fluminea</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 0/1; Zalužice; 48.7639, 21.9753; water reservoir shore after water level drops; 18. 12. 2024; 110; J. Fedorčák leg., B. Tej det.
<i>Corbicula fluminea</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 20/64; Lúčky; 48.7770, 22.0397; water reservoir shore after water level drops; 18. 12. 2024; 111; J. Fedorčák leg., B. Tej det.
<i>Corbicula fluminea</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 9/20; Jovsa; 48.8099, 22.0834; water reservoir shore after water level drops; 18. 12. 2024; 115; J. Fedorčák leg., B. Tej det.
<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 10/0; Nitra; 48.3033, 18.0914; Kukučínova Street, in the hedgerow; 16. 5. 2024; 139; P. Purgat
<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 1/0; Nitra; 48.3107, 18.0907; Andreja Šulgana Street; 16. 5. 2024; 140; P. Purgat
<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 1/0; Bratislava; 48.1458, 17.1279; Továrnská Street; 10. 5. 2024; 139; P. Purgat
<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 1/0; Stupava; 48.2743, 17.0280; Marcheggská Street; 20. 8. 2024; 179; H. Čejka, T. Čejka
<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 20/0; Nové Zámky; 47.9897, 18.1628; Šafárikova Street, surroundings of the marketplace; 11. 4. 2024; 115; P. Purgat
<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 1/0; Hoste; 48.2605, 17.6384; in the backgarden; 19. 5. 2024; 125; R. Masarovič
<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 1/0; Krivenice; 50.4055, 14.4393; cycling trail along the river Labe, by the wood factory with the veener production line; 29. 7. 2024; 155; L. Beran
<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 1/0; Pezinok; 48.2860, 17.2668; Hrnčiarska Street, on the house wall by the parking lot; 1. 8. 2024; 157; T. Navara leg., T. Čejka det.
<i>Cornu aspersum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 4/0; Krivenice; 50.4055, 14.4393; cycling trail along the river Labe, by the wood factory with the veener production line; 9. 8. 2024; 155; L. Beran
<i>Dreissena rostriformis</i> (Deshayes, 1838); 1/2; Komárno; 47.773148, 18.139259; river Váh; 2. 8. 2024; 107; J. Čačaný leg., M. Horsák det.
<i>Euglesa globularis</i> (Clessin, 1873); 22/0; Toužín; 49.0683, 15.4287; the wetland by the river Moravská Dyje; 2. 9. 2024; 458; L. Beran
<i>Euglesa pseudosphaerium</i> (J. Favre, 1927); 2/0; Ražice; 49.2527, 14.0990; a flooded alderwoods on the E edge of the Řežabinec National Nature Monument; 23. 11. 2024; 367; L. Beran (BERAN 2025)
<i>Euglesa pseudosphaerium</i> (J. Favre, 1927); 150/0; Ražice; 49.2541, 14.0986; a S part of the overgrown N pool on the E edge of the Řežabinec National Nature Monument; 23. 11. 2024; 367; L. Beran (BERAN 2025)

<i>Euglesa pseudosphaerium</i> (J. Favre, 1927); 40/0; Ražice; 49.2514, 14.0972; a S part of the extensive S pool on the E edge of the Řežabinec National Nature Monument; 23. 11. 2024; 367; L. Beran (BERAN 2025)
<i>Euglesa pseudosphaerium</i> (J. Favre, 1927); 70/0; Ražice; 49.2522, 14.0976; a N part of the extensive S pool on the E edge of the Řežabinec National Nature Monument; 27. 10. 2024; 367; L. Beran (BERAN 2025)
<i>Euglesa pseudosphaerium</i> (J. Favre, 1927); 3/0; Ražice; 49.2533, 14.0980; a small pool opposite of the bird observatory on the E edge of the Řežabinec National Nature Monument; 27. 10. 2024; 367; L. Beran (BERAN 2025)
<i>Euglesa pseudosphaerium</i> (J. Favre, 1927); 2/0; Ražice; 49.2517, 14.0836; reeds in the SW edge of the pond Řežabinec; 26. 10. 2024; 367; L. Beran (BERAN 2025)
<i>Euglesa pseudosphaerium</i> (J. Favre, 1927); 40/0; Ražice; 49.2484, 14.0947; reeds in the SE edge of the pond Řežabinec; 26. 10. 2024; 367; L. Beran (BERAN 2025)
<i>Euglesa pseudosphaerium</i> (J. Favre, 1927); 30/0; Ražice; 49.2566, 14.0979; reeds in the SE edge of the pond Řežabinec; 26. 10. 2024; 367; L. Beran (BERAN 2025)
<i>Euglesa pseudosphaerium</i> (J. Favre, 1927); 4/0; Ražice; 49.2545, 14.0831; wetlands in the W part of the pond Řežabinec; 26. 10. 2024; 367; L. Beran (BERAN 2025)
<i>Euglesa pseudosphaerium</i> (J. Favre, 1927); 10/0; Ražice; 49.2547, 14.0985; a N part of the N pool on the E edge of the Řežabinec National Nature Monument; 26. 10. 2024; 367; L. Beran (BERAN 2025)
<i>Ferrissia californica</i> (Rowell, 1863); 3/0; Velký Luh; 50.2023, 12.3697; the N edge of the sandpit; 21. 7. 2024; 475; K. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Ferrissia californica</i> (Rowell, 1863); 3/0; Velký Luh; 50.2034, 12.3683; the sewage pond near Velký Luh; 21. 7. 2024; 480; K. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Ferrissia californica</i> (Rowell, 1863); 2/0; Spálená; 50.2189, 12.4120; a pond; 21. 7. 2024; 472; K. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Gyraulus parvus</i> (Say, 1817); 30/0; Vejprty; 50.4634, 13.1288; the bay of the reservoir Přísečnice; 5. 10. 2024; 738; K. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Gyraulus parvus</i> (Say, 1817); 35/0; Vejprty; 50.4562, 13.1365; the bay of the reservoir Přísečnice by the inflow of Hamerský potok; 5. 10. 2024; 738; K. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Gyraulus parvus</i> (Say, 1817); 40/0; Velký Luh; 50.2023, 12.3697; the N edge of the sandpit; 21. 7. 2024; 475; K. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Gyraulus rossmaessleri</i> (Auerswald, 1852); 8/0; Nové Modlany; 50.6723, 13.8693; a ditch by the small stream Zálužanský potok; 19. 5. 2024; 220; L. Beran
<i>Gyraulus rossmaessleri</i> (Auerswald, 1852); 4/0; Nové Modlany; 50.6720, 13.8671; a small sedge wetland in the alderwood; 19. 5. 2024; 219; L. Beran
<i>Gyraulus rossmaessleri</i> (Auerswald, 1852); 17/0; Bohosudov; 50.6729, 13.8876; a sedge wetland on the edge of a meadow; 19. 5. 2024; 202; L. Beran
<i>Helix lucorum</i> Linnaeus, 1758; 20/0; Nitra; 48.3150, 18.1150; Levická Street; 18. 5. 2024; 174; K. Juričková
<i>Helix lucorum</i> Linnaeus, 1758; 15/0; Nitra; 48.3153, 18.0988; Nábřežie mládeže Street, in the kindergarten area; 17. 5. 2024; 175; P. Vörösová
<i>Hygromia cinctella</i> (Draparnaud, 1801); 1/0; Tesárske Mlyňany; 48.3518, 18.3774; the area of the decorative stones shop; 22. 10. 2024; 171; J. Čapka leg., T. Čejka det.
<i>Hygromia cinctella</i> (Draparnaud, 1801); 30/0; Brno; 49.1927, 16.5956; lawn with <i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i> and <i>Ailanthus altissima</i> on the Úvoz Street, below castle Špilberk and adjacent Pivovarská Street; 24. 5. 2025; 215; R. Coufal
<i>Hygromia cinctella</i> (Draparnaud, 1801); 5/0; Bratislava ; 48.1578, 17.0999; Na Kalvárii Street; 10. 9. 2024; 233; D. R. Letz (LETZ 2024)
<i>Krynickyllus melanocephalus</i> Kaleniczenko, 1851; 2/0; Prešov, Cemjata ; 48.9813, 21.1897; in the area of the former arboretum Ortáše; 29. 10. 2024; 400; M. Nandrážiová leg., T. Čejka det.
<i>Krynickyllus melanocephalus</i> Kaleniczenko, 1851; >30; Lučatín; 48.7836, 19.3236; cemetery; 18. 10. 2024; 450; M. Čiliak
<i>Krynickyllus melanocephalus</i> Kaleniczenko, 1851; 10/0; Praha – Dejvice; 50.1164, 14.3745; Dolní Šárka, edge of the Dolní Šárka Nature Monument and in the surrounding deciduous forest; 7. 10. 2024; 200; D. Říhová, A. Kocurková leg., L. Juričková det. (ŘÍHOVÁ et al. 2025)
<i>Krynickyllus melanocephalus</i> Kaleniczenko, 1851; 1/0; Hradec Králové; 50.18629, 15.84123; path through the suburban meadow; 12. 10. 2024; 235; A. Kaupová (KAUPOVÁ 2024)

<i>Krynickyllus melanocephalus</i> Kaleniczenko, 1851; many; Praha – Dolní Šárka; 50.1176731, 14.3797542; Dolní Šárka, the bases of the hillside in the deciduous forest above the stream; 24. 10. 2024; 205; D. Říhová (ŘÍHOVÁ et al. 2025)
<i>Krynickyllus melanocephalus</i> Kaleniczenko, 1851; >30; Prešov; 48.9844, 21.2295; Narcis gardening area, deciduous forest; 7. 10. 2024; 262; B. Tej
<i>Krynickyllus melanocephalus</i> Kaleniczenko, 1851; 3; Hervartov; 49.2510, 21.2059; ravine between fields, mixed forest; 5. 11. 2024; 432; B. Tej
<i>Krynickyllus melanocephalus</i> Kaleniczenko, 1851; 6; Hervartov; 49.2487, 21.2072; in the backgarden; 29. 10. 2024; 451; B. Tej
<i>Krynickyllus melanocephalus</i> Kaleniczenko, 1851; 38; Hervartov; 49.2514, 21.2311; field margin near a water reservoir; 28. 9. 2024; 352; B. Tej
<i>Melanoides tuberculata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 5; Turčianske Teplice; 48.86039, 18.83868; the stream Čepčinský potok; 5. 5. 2023; 509; V. Janský leg., J. Čačaný det.
<i>Melanoides tuberculata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 12; Bystričany – Chalmová; 48.6701, 18.49506; canal Chalmová; 5. 5. 2023; 216; V. Janský leg., J. Čačaný det.
<i>Melanoides tuberculata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); >100; Dukovany; 49.0949, 16.1535; the stream Skryjský potok flowing off of cooling water reservoir below nuclear power plant; 20. 5. 2024; 330; R. Coufal (COUFAL & BERAN 2024)
<i>Odhneripisidium moitessierianum</i> (Paladilhe, 1866); 2/0; Budyně nad Ohří; 50.4029, 14.1173; the canal Malá Ohře; 13. 4. 2024; 156; J. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Oxychilus translucidus</i> (Mortillet, 1853); 16/27; Brno; 49.2046, 16.5964; Kotlářská 2, Faculty of Science, Botanical garden, tropical greenhouse; 8. 4. 2024; 250; M. Horsák (Fig. 7)
<i>Pisidium amnicum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 14/0; Staré Hobzí; 49.0167, 15.4265; the stream Bolíkovský potok ca 300 m upstream of its inflow into the Moravská Dyje; 1. 9. 2024; 447; L. Beran
<i>Pisidium amnicum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 13/0; Staré Hobzí; 49.0169, 15.4248; the stream Bolíkovský potok on the W edge of the Moravská Dyje Nature Monument; 1. 9. 2024; 448; L. Beran
<i>Pisidium amnicum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 4/0; Staré Hobzí; 49.0163, 15.4273; the stream Bolíkovský potok upstream of its inflow into the Moravská Dyje; 1. 9. 2024; 446; L. Beran
<i>Pisidium amnicum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 4/0; Košnice; 50.4006, 13.9439; the river Ohře downstream of the weir; 18. 8. 2024; 175; J. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Pisidium amnicum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 10/0; Budyně nad Ohří; 50.4029, 14.1173; the canal Malá Ohře; 13. 4. 2024; 156; J. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Pisidium amnicum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774); 8/0; Budyně nad Ohří; 50.4039, 14.1075; the canal Malá Ohře to the W of Budyně nad Ohří; 13. 4. 2024; 156; J. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Planorbis carinatus</i> O. F. Müller, 1774; 6/0; Vnorovice; 49.0365, 15.4332; the river Moravská Dyje downstream of the weir ; 2. 9. 2024; 446; L. Beran
<i>Planorbis carinatus</i> O. F. Müller, 1774; 3/0; Košnice; 50.4006, 13.9439; the river Ohře downstream of the weir; 18. 8. 2024; 175; J. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Potamopyrgus antipodarum</i> (Gray, 1843); 3/0; Olomouc; 49.5981, 17.2929; river Bystřice, on gravel bottom; 7. 9. 2024; 214; M. Mañas
<i>Potamopyrgus antipodarum</i> (Gray, 1843); 35/0; Přepře; 50.5814, 15.1127; the river Jizera downstream of the weir; 13. 10. 2024; 248; J. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Potamopyrgus antipodarum</i> (Gray, 1843); 4/0; Písečné; 48.9507, 15.4699; the river Moravská Dyje ca 300 m downstream of the weir ; 31. 8. 2024; 430; L. Beran
<i>Potamopyrgus antipodarum</i> (Gray, 1843); 7/0; Písečné; 48.9488, 15.4716; the river Moravská Dyje on the Czech-Austrian boundaries; 31. 8. 2024; 430; L. Beran
<i>Pupilla triplicata</i> (Studer, 1820); 2/4; Koněprusy; 49.9125, 14.0820; the S part of the Kobyla quarry, the slope overgrown with shrubs and trees below the south-facing rocky outcrop.; 5. 6. 2024; 430; A. Kocurková, L. Juříčková
<i>Sinanodonta woodiana</i> (Lea, 1834); 1/0; Bohumín; 49.9294, 18.3484; Hraniční meandry Odry Nature Monument, oxbow of the Odra river; 20. 8. 2024; 190; E. Šlachtová
<i>Sinanodonta woodiana</i> (Lea, 1834); 0/2; Zachotín; 49.4558, 15.3433; the SE part of the pond Dolní Kladiny; 11. 5. 2024; 528; L. Beran
<i>Sinanodonta woodiana</i> (Lea, 1834); 0/5; Zachotín; 49.4558, 15.3433; the SE part of the pond Dolní Kladiny; 10. 2. 2024; 528; L. Beran

<i>Sinanodonta woodiana</i> (Lea, 1834); 0/2; Zachotín; 49.4525, 15.3360; the S edge of the pond Dolní Kladiny; 10. 2. 2024; 528; L. Beran
<i>Sinanodonta woodiana</i> (Lea, 1834); 0/3; Vinné; 48.7962, 21.9779; litoral of the water reservoir; 12. 12. 2024; 115; B. Tej
<i>Sinanodonta woodiana</i> (Lea, 1834); 0/5; Hraň; 48.5355, 21.8058; river Ondava, S of the village; 9. 9. 2024; 100; B. Tej
<i>Sinanodonta woodiana</i> (Lea, 1834); 1/11; Hraň; 48.5394, 21.8031; river Trnávka; 9. 9. 2024; 102; B. Tej
<i>Sinanodonta woodiana</i> (Lea, 1834); 19/3; Ladmovce; 48.3965, 21.7639; confluence of canal Somotor and river Bodrog; 5. 9. 2024; 95; B. Tej
<i>Sinanodonta woodiana</i> (Lea, 1834); 61/202; Stretávka; 48.6074, 21.9944; pumping station Čierna Voda; 3. 9. 2024; 100; B. Tej
<i>Sinanodonta woodiana</i> (Lea, 1834); 0/4; Jovsa; 48.8099, 22.0834; water reservoir shore after water level drops; 18. 12. 2024; 115; J. Fedorčák leg., B. Tej det.
<i>Sinanodonta woodiana</i> (Lea, 1834); 27/0; Iňačovce; 48.6831, 22.0619; drainage channel; 28. 10. 2024; 98; B. Tej
<i>Sphaerium nucleus</i> (Studer, 1820); 3/0; Ražice; 49.2527, 14.0990; a flooded alderwoods on the E edge of the Řežabinec National Nature Monument; 23. 11. 2024; 367; L. Beran (BERAN 2025)
<i>Sphaerium nucleus</i> (Studer, 1820); 6/0; Polná; 49.4982, 15.7088; pools in the floodplain of the Šlapanka; 17. 11. 2024; 467; L. Beran
<i>Sphaerium nucleus</i> (Studer, 1820); 10/0; Dobronín; 49.4739, 15.6412; wetlands by the S edge of the pond Valchař; 16. 11. 2024; 465; L. Beran
<i>Sphaerium nucleus</i> (Studer, 1820); 4/0; Ražice; 49.2533, 14.0980; a small pool opposite of the bird observatory on the E edge of the Řežabinec National Nature Monument; 27. 10. 2024; 367; L. Beran (BERAN 2025)
<i>Sphaerium nucleus</i> (Studer, 1820); 6/0; Bakov nad Jizerou; 50.4866, 14.9326; an oxbow of the river Jizera; 21. 5. 2024; 215; L. Beran
<i>Sphaerium nucleus</i> (Studer, 1820); 3/0; Střítež; 49.4675, 15.6282; the W edge of the pond Mlýnský rybník; 9. 3. 2024; 475; L. Beran
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1831); 1/0; Zavar; 48.3521, 17.6664; under the bricks that line the flower bed; 21. 5. 2024; 145; M. Budzáková leg., T. Čejka det.
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1831); 10/0; Komárno; 47.7650, 18.1175; cemetery; 14. 6. 2024; 110; M. Čiliak
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1831); 7/0; Marcelová; 47.7936, 18.2848; cemetery; 14. 6. 2024; 120; M. Čiliak
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1831); 10/0; Slovenská Lúпча; 48.7693, 19.2761; cemetery; 16. 6. 2024; 400; M. Čiliak
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1831); 20/0; Piešťany; 48.5876, 17.8124; cemetery; 19. 9. 2024; 160; M. Čiliak
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1831); 40/0; Moravany nad Váhom; 48.6016, 17.8644; cemetery; 19. 9. 2024; 200; M. Čiliak
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1831); >70; Partizánske; 48.6353, 18.3928; cemetery; 19. 9. 2024; 210; M. Čiliak
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1831); 20/0; Veľké Uherce; 48.6157, 18.4318; cemetery; 19. 9. 2024; 230; M. Čiliak
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1831); 20/0; Detva; 48.5640, 19.4245; cemetery; 30. 9. 2024; 450; M. Čiliak (Fig. 5)
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1831); 1/0; Kriváň; 48.5293, 19.4607; cemetery; 30. 9. 2024; 430; M. Čiliak
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1831); >50; Kalša; 48.6161, 21.5327; railway station; 15. 5. 2024; 211; A. Mock
<i>Tandonia kusceri</i> (H. Wagner, 1831); 38/0; Brno; 49.1927, 16.5955; lawn with <i>Aesculus hippocastanus</i> and <i>Ailanthus altissima</i> on the Úvoz Street, below castle Špilberk and adjacent Pivovarská Street; 24. 5. 2024; 215; R. Coufal
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 1/0; Sázavka; 49.7321, 15.3965; the stream Sázavka ca 200 m upstream of a road; 20. 10. 2024; 428; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 7/0; Dolní Dlužiny; 49.7197, 15.4095; the stream Sázavka to the SE of Dolní Dlužiny; 20. 10. 2024; 428; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 24/0; Kunemil; 49.7078, 15.4207; the stream Sázavka opposite of the small house; 19. 10. 2024; 415; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 1/0; Staré Hobzí; 49.0076, 15.4372; the river Moravská Dyje upstream of the castle Janov; 1. 9. 2024; 446; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 2/0; Modletice; 48.9778, 15.4580; the river Moravská Dyje in Modletice; 1. 9. 2024; 442; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 1/0; Písečné; 48.9636, 15.4643; the river Moravská Dyje in Písečné; 1. 9. 2024; 442; L. Beran

<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 4/0; Modletice; 48.9788, 15.4539; the river Moravská Dyje near Modletice; 31. 8. 2024; 439; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 8/0; Písečné; 48.9507, 15.4699; the river Moravská Dyje ca 300 m downstream of the weir; 31. 8. 2024; 430; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 6/0; Písečné; 48.9516, 15.4712; the river Moravská Dyje ca 100 m downstream of the weir; 31. 8. 2024; 431; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 80/0; Písečné; 48.9488, 15.4716; the river Moravská Dyje on the Czech-Austrian boundaries; 31. 8. 2024; 430; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 1/0; Sedčice; 50.3105, 13.4427; the stream Liboc by the bridge in Sedčice; 25. 8. 2024; 230; K. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 5/0; Žabokliky; 50.3179, 13.4576; the stream Liboc by the bridge near Žabokliky; 25. 8. 2024; 228; K. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 8/0; Libočany; 50.3283, 13.4981; the stream Liboc to the W of Libočany; 25. 8. 2024; 215; K. Beran leg., L. Beran det.
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 30/0; Dubovice; 49.4390, 15.1654; the stream Hejlovka to the NW of Dubovice; 11. 8. 2024; 520; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 1/0; Vlásenice; 49.4244, 15.1638; the stream Cerekvický potok by the bridge; 11. 8. 2024; 525; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 1/0; Vlásenice; 49.4254, 15.166; the stream Hejlovka by the confluence with the Cerekvický potok; 11. 8. 2024; 525; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 15/0; Hodějovice; 49.4705, 15.2059; the stream Hejlovka by the bridge; 10. 8. 2024; 470; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 5/0; Kojčice; 49.4825, 15.2486; the stream Hejlovka by the bridge near Prokopův Mlýn; 10. 8. 2024; 460; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 0/1; Světlá nad Sázavou; 49.6664, 15.4056; the river Sázava downstream of the weir; 10. 8. 2024; 395; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 80/0; Čakovice; 49.4601, 15.1738; the stream Hejlovka by the bridge near Čakovický Mlýn; 10. 8. 2024; 490; L. Beran
<i>Unio crassus</i> Philipsson, 1788 / <i>Unio nanus</i> Lamarck, 1819; 13/0; Čakovice; 49.4721, 15.1848; the stream Hejlovka by the bridge of the road Pelhřimov – Červená Řečice; 10. 8. 2024; 490; L. Beran
<i>Vertigo geyeri</i> Lindholm, 1925; 1/0; Hluboká u Borovan; 48.8918, 14.6882; Žemlička Nature Monument, alkaline fen; 18. 6. 2024; 480; M. Hájek leg., M. Horsák det.
<i>Viviparus acerosus</i> (Bourguignat, 1862); 0/9; Zachotín; 49.4558, 15.3433; the SE part of the pond Dolní Kladiny; 10. 2. 2024; 528; L. Beran